

Fabrication and application of voltammetric electrodes for determination of platinum in aqueous medium from artificial samples of its precursors

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Manuscript received online 09 July 2014, revised 03 September 2014, accepted 14 October 2014

Abstract : Electrochemical methods differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry (DPASV) and cyclic voltammetry (CV) were applied to determine the concentration of platinum ions in aqueous solutions. Different working electrodes were used in combination with platinum as an auxiliary and standard calomel as a reference electrode. Various parameters such as pH, buffer system, time of deposition, N₂ purging and potential scan ranges were optimized to get improved results. Modification of electrode surface and fabrication of past electrodes overcome the problems of adsorption and pre-concentration of metal ions at the surface of the electrode. The developed method was successfully applied to artificial samples of ores and rocks. The low detection limit (LDL) 1.4×10^{-04} µg/ml and linear regression coefficient 0.9906 were noticed for a concentration range 0.001–2 µg/ml of platinum.

Keywords : Platinum, voltammetry, modified electrodes, rocks, ores, artificial samples.

Introduction

Platinum is considered as a precious metal due to its economic values, rare existence in its precursors, and high public demand¹. Platinum has distinctive properties and industrial/medical applications^{2–4}. Moreover, Pt is environmentally significant and is used to reduce and control the emission of carbon monoxide gas as evolving from various sources due to combustion. In addition to being a symbol of status and power, Pt group metals are also used in dental and medical applications to treat different diseases as, cancer, arthritis and production of denture^{5–7}. Different instruments and methods, such as graphite-furnace atomic-absorption spectrometry (GFAAS)⁸, titrimetric methods⁹, radiochemical neutron activation analysis¹⁰, emission spectrometry¹¹, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICPMS)¹², reversed-phase liquid chromatography¹³, electro-thermal atomic absorption

spectrometry (ET-AAS)¹⁴, fire assay fusion method¹⁵, gel permeation chromatography¹⁶ and electrochemical techniques^{17–19} have been used to determine Pt from its precursors.

In the current study simple, robust, selective and highly sensitive voltammetric electrodes were fabricated and applied to the determination of platinum in aqueous solutions.

Results and discussion

Optimization of conditions : In the undertaken study, different conditions like pH^{20–31}, deposition time^{19,30–41}, nitrogen purging time^{26,33,34,43–45} were optimized (Fig. 1).

Comparison of peak signals : The voltammograms recorded with different working electrodes were compared to notice the best results for platinum determina-

Fig. 1. Optimization of conditions.

tion^{26,46-52} (Fig. 2).

Calibration curves/plots : The concentration range was additive from 0.001–2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 0.05–4.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.01–4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for CMCPE, GCBE and GCME respectively (Figs. 3-4). The linear regression coefficient value in each case was; (a) $R^2_{\text{GCME-a}} = 0.9989$, (b) $R^2_{\text{GCME-b}} = 0.9983$, (c) $R^2_{\text{GCBE-a}} = 0.9984$ and (d) $R^2_{\text{GCBE-b}} = 0.9952$. LDL was calculated as per procedure^{53,54}. The values of $\text{LDL}_{(\text{CMCPE})} = 1.4 \times 10^{-4} \mu\text{g/ml}$, $\text{LDL}_{(\text{GCBE})} = 6 \times 10^{-4} \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $\text{LDL}_{(\text{GCME})} = 2 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g/ml}$ were determined in each case.

Fig. 2. Comparison of peak signals; voltammograms (A_1 and A_2), (B_1 and B_2), via GCME; and voltammogram (C) were recorded with GCBE, GCME and CMCPE respectively; concentration of Pt^{II} , 1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, current range; 4 mA/cm, scan rate; 100 mV/s, N_2 purged time, 10 min; deposition time, 3 min; potential scan range; -0.3 to 0.2 V, pH, 1.8 ± 0.1 .

Cyclic voltammetry : In Fig. 5, the cyclic voltammogram reveals that quasi-reversible redox reaction takes place at the surface of electrode⁵⁵.

Application of method : The method was applied to different samples of rocks and ores, as mentioned in Table

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Figs. 3-4. Calibration plots recorded for platinum at GCBE and GCME; current range; 4 $\mu\text{A/cm}$, scan rate; 100 mV/s, potential scan range; -0.3 to 0.2 V, N_2 purged time; 10 min, deposition time; 3 min, pH; 1.8 ± 0.1 , Buffer system; $[0.1 \text{ M} (\text{KCl-HCl})]$ with $0.005 \text{ M} \text{ NH}_3$ as supporting electrolytes and for pH adjustment.

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammogram showing redox peak signals for platinum; peak potential difference; $E_{\text{oxd}} - E_{\text{red}} = 32 \text{ mV}$, Current range; $10 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}$, scan rate; $100 \text{ mV}/\text{s}$, N_2 purged time; 10 min, deposition time; 3 min, potential scan range; -0.3 to 0.2 V , pH; 1.8 ± 0.1 .

1 and Table 2. The platinum was not detected in the real samples of different rocks and ores. Thus, artificial samples

were prepared by spiking different concentrations of platinum in some rocks and ores samples (Table 3).

Experimental

Equipments and chemicals : A Swiss-made Precisa balance (Model-XB 120A), controlled-temperature furnace (Model 810-00-002), an electric oven (Model 8559), A WTW inoLab model pH meter, waveform generator (PP RI, HI-TEK Instruments, England, UK) with a potentiostat, an electrochemical cell and an X-Y recorder were used in routine analyses. All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. A 1% chitosan solution was prepared by dissolving 0.01 g chitosan in 1 ml of 2 M acetic acid solution.

Sampling profile : Rocks samples with particular nature and chemical composition were collected from various locations in Pakistan (Table 1). While, ores samples were obtained from the Mineral Testing Laboratory

Table 1. Samples of different rocks collected from diverse areas of Pakistan

Sample code	Site of collection	Physical appearance	Remarks
R ₁	Bakka Khail (NWA)	Brownish	Metamorphic basic rocks and sedimentary rocks
R ₂	Miran Shah (NWA)	Purple	
R ₃	Mir Ali (NWA)	Dark gray	
R ₄	Karak (KPK)	Gray	
R ₅	Dara Pezzo (KPK)	Dark brown	
Samples collected from PCSIR Laboratories, Karachi (Sindh)			
R ₆	Jam Khan jo Vandio (Sindh)	Pink	Igneous rock
R ₇		Dark blue	
R ₈		Light blue	
R ₉	Ramji jo Vandio (Sindh)	Dark green (Maleno Cratic)	Fined grained basic rock
R ₁₀		Light pink (Leuco Cratic)	Coarse grain granite rock
R ₁₁		- do -	- do -
R ₁₂	Paradaro (Sindh)	Dark gray	Basic rocks
R ₁₃		Light gray	
R ₁₄		Gray	
R ₁₅		- do -	Granite with feldlaths
R ₁₆	Mukrio	Dark green (Hyper Malenium)	Basic rocks
R ₁₇	Kasbo	- do -	- do -
R ₁₈	On jo Vandio (Sindh)	Dark red	Ferrogenous sand stone of Barthala formation
R ₁₉		Yellow	
R ₂₀	Zardari Mine Nagar Parkar	Dark red	- do -

NWA = North Waziristan Agency, KPK = Khyber Pukhtunkhwa.

Table 2. Ores samples collected from MTL, Peshawar, KPK

Sr. no.	Ore sample	Composition	Colour
1.	Boulangerite	Pb ₅ Sb ₄ S ₁₁	Blue and grey to brown
2.	Stibnite	Sb ₂ S ₃	Dark grey
3.	Magnetite	Fe ₃ O ₄	Purple
4.	Scheelite	Ca[WO ₄]	Greenish grey

MTL = Mineral Testing Laboratories.

Table 3. Analyses of artificial samples preparation

Sample no.	Pt ^{II} added (µg/ml)	Pt ^{II} found (µg/ml)	Recovery (%)
S ₀	0.0	0.0	0.0
S ₁	0.5	0.472	96.4
S ₂	1	0.973	97.3
S ₃	2	1.890	94.5

S₀ - S₃ = Artificial samples of rocks and ores.

(MTL), Peshawar (Table 2).

Analytical method : The ores and rocks samples were converted into powder form and processed through fire assay method followed by acid digestion. The glassy carbon modified electrode (GCME) was prepared by applying a drop of 1% chitosan on the electrode's surface. The chemically modified carbon paste electrode (CMCPE) was constructed by packing a uniform slurry of 0.1 g homovanilic acid, 0.2 g graphite powder and 0.2 g paraffin oils (Fig. 6). A three electrodes system, (i) GCE/GCME/CMCPE, as a working, (ii) saturated calomel, as a reference electrode and (iii) platinum, as an auxiliary electrode were immersed into an electrochemical cell containing 10 ml of aqueous solution. Nitrogen gas was purged to remove the oxygen. The solution was electrolyzed under controlled conditions and voltammograms were recorded.

Fig. 6. Optimization of conditions.

Conclusion

pH, and dissolved oxygen greatly affect the electrochemical analyses of metals. The developed method is highly sensitive to the ionic species of platinum. The high selectivity and sensitivity of GCME may be due to the organic ligand used for its surface modification. The recording of single voltammogram with CMCPE showed its response to the total amount of metal ions rather than the ionized species with variable oxidation state.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to appreciate the Higher Education Commission (HEC), Islamabad, Pakistan for research support fellowship program, and the Deanship of Scientific Research at King Saud University for its funding of this research through the Research Group Project no. RGP-VPP-255. The authors also extend their gratitude to Director and staff members of MTL for providing some important ores samples.

References

1. S. Bekir, C. Omur, D. Serhat and D. Mehmet, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2007, **587**, 272.
2. N. N. Greenwood and A. Earnshaw, "Chemistry of the Elements", Maxwell Machmillan International Editions, ISBN : 0-02-946091-3, 1st ed., 1984, 1328.
3. Afzal Shah, "Electrochemical Evaluation and Recovery of Precious Metals from Ores and Rocks Samples", NCEAC, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan, 2008.
4. G. Laurence, "Lost Secrets of the Sacred Ark; Amazing Revelations on the Incredible Power of Gold", Harper Collins, London, 2003.
5. F. Rani, L. H. Khan, F. Mahmood and Z. M. Iqbal, *Pak. J. Sci. Indust. Res.*, 1998, **41**, 140.
6. M. Cox, A. A. Pichugin, E. I. El-Shafey and Q. Appleton, *Hydrometallurgy*, 2005, **78**, 137.
7. Martin Harper and Julie M. Siegel, *J. Air and Waste Manag. Asso.*, 2003, **53**, 434.
8. J. G. S. Gupta, *Talanta*, 1989, **36**, 651.
9. W. S. Selig, *Microchem. J.*, 1990, **41**, 302.
10. D. Wildhagen and V. Krivan, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1993, **274**, 257.
11. V. Otruba, M. Strnadova and B. Skalnikova, *Talanta*, 1993, **40**, 221.
12. O. Mihaly, M. Gabor, Z. Michaela, V. Istvan, S. Ilse, M. G. Victor, T. Eniko, C. Sergio and Z. Gyula, *Microchem. J.*, 2007, **87**, 159.
13. Q. Liu, J. Liu, Y. Tong and J. Cheng, *Anal. Chim.*

- Acta*, 1992, **269**, 223.
14. F. R. Sanchez, C. O. Bosch and J. M. P. Cano, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **18**, 1270.
 15. T. Paukert and I. Rubeska, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1993, **278**, 125.
 16. J. Messerschmidt, F. Alt and G. Tolg, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1994, **291**, 161.
 17. X. Canhui, X. Qingji, H. Jiming and Y. Shouzhuo, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2005, **584**, 201.
 18. P. Sharma and A. Agarwal, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2005, **21**, 129.
 19. L. Yi-Heng, X. Hong-Qi and Z. Fang-Qin, *Talanta*, 2005, **67**, 28.
 20. D. D. Perrin and D. Boyd, "Buffers for pH and Metal Ion Control", Chapman and Hall Ltd., 11 New Fetter Lane, London EC4P4EE, ISBN# 0-412-21890-9, 1979, 2.
 21. R. J. Dawson and G. H. Kelsall, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2007, **37**, 3.
 22. W. J. Bruckard, K. J. McDonald, C. M. McInnes, G. J. Sparrow and J. T. Woodlock, *Hydrometall.*, 1992, **30**, 211.
 23. D. Serhat, M. Savas, D. Mehmet and S. Bekir, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **553**, 73.
 24. A. M. Buswell, D. J. Bradshaw, P. J. Harris and Z. Ekmekci, *Miner. Eng.*, 2002, **15**, 395.
 25. K. Hoppstock and M. Michulitz, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1997, **350**, 135.
 26. Y. Xianzeng, Y. Qinghua, W. Yan and L. Nanqiang, *Talanta*, 1998, **47**, 1099.
 27. C. Mack, B. Wilhelmi, J. R. Duncan and J. E. Burgess, *Biotech. Advanc.*, 2007, **25**, 264.
 28. C. Philippe, V. Thierry, M. S. Jose, M. E. Lynne and G. Eric, *Hydrometallurgy*, 2005, **76**, 131.
 29. K. S. Kyung, L. K. Churl, L. J. Chun, R. K. In, S. H. Joon and K. Tak, *Resourcing Processing*, 2004, **51**, 48.
 30. P. Yong, N. A. Rowson, J. P. G. Farr, I. R. Harris and L. E. Macaskie, *Env. Tech.*, 2003, **24**, 289.
 31. H. G. Julsing and R. I. McCrindle, *Water Sci. Tech.*, 2000, **42**, 63.
 32. S. Masafumi, S. Tomoyoshi and Y. Noboru, *Electr. Eng. Japan*, 2007, **158**, 1.
 33. M. Alireza and T. A. Mohammad, *Talanta*, 2007, **71**, 615.
 34. S. K. Reza Karimi and B. K. Mohsen, *Talanta*, 2006, **69**, 741.
 35. V. Reyes-Cruz, I. Gonzalez and M. T. Oropeza, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2004, **49**, 4417.
 36. N. P. Brandon, D. Pilone¹, G. H. Kelsall and Q. Yin, *J. Appl. Electrochem.*, 2003, **33**, 853.
 37. D. Pletcher and F. C. Walsh, "Indust. Electrochem"., 2nd ed., 1990, pp. 8-55, 210, 424-426.
 38. S. Santhanamahalingam, A. Akintayo, S. Ramiah and A. W. D. Robert, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2008, **10**, 141.
 39. P. Allongue and E. Souteyrand, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1990, **286**, 217.
 40. Y. L. Kawamura, T. Sakka and Y. H. Ogata, *Meeting Abstracts*, 2004, 25.
 41. S. M. Mahmoud, W. W. John and A. G. Badr, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1995, **142**, 4113.
 42. S. K. Reza and B. K. Mohsen, *Talanta*, 2006, **69**, 741.
 43. S. Hyosul and K. Chan, *Anal. Sci.*, 2003, **19**, 1667.
 44. W. Mi-Sook, Y. Jeong-Sik, Y. Jang-Hee, J. Euh-Duck and S. Yoon-Bo, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **24**, 948.
 45. D. Fabiana, S. J. Juana, A. H. Alejandro and S. E. Leonides, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2000, **494**, 60.
 46. A. M. Demkin, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2001, **56**, 1051.
 47. M. J. Ronald, N. N. Irishi, B. S. Sherigara, R. K. Vijayakumar and K. Reddy, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2006, **118**, 275.
 48. S. Ivan, G. Michal and V. Karel, *Talanta*, 2007, **72**, 512.
 49. W. Chunming, Z. Haoli, S. Yi and L. Hulin, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1998, **361**, 133.
 50. Z. Navratilova and P. Kula, *Anal. Chm. Acta*, 1993, **273**, 305.
 51. H. Grégoire, B. Valerio, D. H. Patrick, B. Thomas and A. M. W. Damián, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **511**, 137.
 52. V. Ivanova and C. Buess-Herman, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2003, **552**, 45.
 53. L. Clinio, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2006, **557**, 70.
 54. D. Elio, B. Barbara and C. Raffaella, *Electroanal.*, 2004, **16**, 304.
 55. A. M. Bond, *Broad. Electrochem. Horiz.*, ISBN 019850477 2 (PbK), Oxford University Press Inc, New York, 2002, 59.

